

A STUDY ON MARKETING OF SUDHA DAIRY IN PURNEA DISTRICT OF BIHAR

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Abstract

The present study entitled "Marketing channel involve in marketing of Sudha Dairy Milk" was undertaken to study In this study, an attempt has been made to study analysis of Procurement of raw milk for Patna Dairy project is done from the rural areas of five districts of Bihar through one channel only. Marketing of liquid milk is done in the town parts of the five districts of Bihar through two channels. Every producer has their own cattle and buffaloes. Jersey breed of cows are highest in number (52%) while in case of buffaloes, local breeds (72%) still wins the race. About 80 per cent of the producers purchase cattle feed, 'Sudha Dairy' for their cattle, which is manufactured by PDP. Only 20 per cent of the producers have used artificial insemination provided by the PDP. Still only 33 per cent of the producers have attended the training programmes conducted by PDP. Only 10 per cent of the consumers are well aware of the toll free consumer's help line number.

Keywords: Supply Chain, Milk, Dairy

Introduction:

The milk production system in India is characterized by large numbers of small and geographically dispersed dairy producers who have marketable surpluses of milk but face diseconomies of scale in marketing it to demand centers in distant urban areas.

Milk distribution in Indian dairy industry begins with the dairy firm processing and sending its packed milk to its wholesalers and then to the retailers and consumers. Time is very crucial factor in the supply of milk as milk due to its perishable nature as the milk will get stale if it is not transported within the stipulated time frame, Hence the transportation and delivery of milk along importance. The various stakeholders of the milk distribution network are wholesalers, retailers, chilling centers, transportation vehicles and milk parlors. In order to make the milk flow system efficient all the links in dairy distribution system need to be streamlined based on the demand.

Supply chain management (SCM) is a rapidly evolving area of interest to academicians and business management practitioners alike. Coordinating the external and internal activities of a firm is the basic philosophy of supply chain management. It is about managing the entire process in a collective and unified fashion. Most of the manufacturing firms are organized as networks of manufacturing and distribution facilities that procure raw materials transform them into intermediate and finished products and distribute the finished products to customers. The simplest network consists of facilities which perform procurement, manufacturing and distribution. These networks are called value added chains or supply chains.

Dairy product, milk and any of the foods made from milk, including butter, cheese, ice cream, yogurt, and condensed and dried milk. Stick of butter. Milk has been used by humans since the beginning of recorded time to provide both fresh and storable nutritious foods.

India is the top country by production of milk in the world. As of 2020, production of milk in India was 194,800 thousand tonnes that accounts for 40.56% of the world's production of milk. The top 5 countries (others are the United States of America, China, Russian Federation, and Brazil) account for 80.80% of it.

Milk is the primary source of nutrition's including protein and lactose. Dairy farming is considered to be a whole environment of reciprocal relations and dependency, re-production and protection of social values. Hence, dairy farms typically consist of high producing dairy cows. Other species used in commercial dairy farming include goats, sheep, and camels.

Agricultural marketing plays an important role not only in stimulating production and consumption, but in accelerating the pace of economic development also. An efficiency marketing system ensures higher level of income for the farmers and widens the markets for the products by taking than the remote corners of the country. Now –a-days most sensitive problem is better solution of problem in the world of marketing management consumer wants better solution of any problems. Benefits and satisfaction the consumer are getting from

goods manufacturing to service generation since the concept of marketing management has changed and now it becomes as consumer oriented. Most of the company tries to develop the technology to improve their product to right place and on right time. By globalization and information reevaluation where free trade is imposed in all over the world, for any company to service in the market its distribution channels should be strong. If the distribution channel of any organization would be sound than only it can be complete with its competitors. As far as this particular organization is concern it produces milk and milk's products which are so perishable in nature. So many products require minimum time reach in the hands of customers beginning from their manufacturing. So, managing sound distribution network is always a crucial job for marketing manager of the concern organization. Because it is the time factor that counts the effectiveness of the manager.

Materials and Methods:

The study entitled "Marketing channel involve in marketing of Sudha Dairy Milk" was undertaken to understand the knowledge and attitude regarding social media of Kota District, Rajasthan.

Study design:

The design of the present study is descriptive one based on survey method. The study attempts to describe and analyse the marketing channel involve in marketing of Sudha Dairy Milk.

Place of the study

Among all 38 districts of Bihar, Purnia district was selected purposely for the present study because the district has large number of consumer of Sudha dairy in study area.

Sample:

10% respondents will be selected randomly on the basis of location and respondents of total 8 Villages near by Banmankhi block, like Akhtiyarpur, Bahora, Dhima, Gangapur, Ekraha, Harmurhi, Pipra and Raghunathpur

From each village, 24 respondents were selected through random sampling method. Thus, constitutes the 120 respondents from 5 villages forms the respondents of the study.

Methods of data collection

The primary data will be collected from consumers, merchants and different agencies through personal interview. The secondary data will be collected from the office of the agricultural department, and different organization websites also helpful.

Statistical analysis:

The following statistical tools were used in the study based on the nature of the data and objectives of the study:

Arithmetic mean

Standard deviation

Percentage analysis

Pearson product moment correlation coefficient

Results and Discussion:

The study entitled “Marketing channel involve in marketing of Sudha Dairy Milk” was undertaken to understand the knowledge and attitude regarding social media. The results are given under the following heads:

It's the path taken by a product from the producer to reach the end consumer through potential intermediaries. These intermediaries can be wholesalers, retailers, distributors and Internet. It exist two different forms of channels, the direct and the indirect one. Through a direct channel the consumer can buy the product directly from the manufacturer. The contrary happens with an indirect channel, the consumer buys the product via a wholesaler or retailer.

Distribution channels are the path products take from their initial manufacturing stage to selling them to consumers.

The main goal of these channels is to make goods available to final consumers in sales outlets as soon as possible.

Distribution channels directly impact a company's [sales](#), so you want to make them as efficient as possible.

Different Distribution channels used by producers

It refers to the various market charges paid by different market agencies and middlemen's share along with producer's share in consumer's price received by producer in different market channels.

Table 3.1: Price Spread for Marketing in Channel- I

(Producer – consumer) Rs. /kg

S.NO.	Particulars	Rs.	Percentage%
1.	Net price received by the producers	350.0	99.79
2.	Marketing cost incurred by producers	0.30	0.10
3.	Total marketing cost	0.30	0.10
4.	Consumer's price	350.60	99.99

Table 3.2: Price Spread for Marketing in Channel- II

(Producer – retailer - consumer) Rs. /kg

S.NO.	Particulars	Rs.	Percentage%
1.	Net price received by the producers	350.1	90.3
2.	Marketing cost incurred by producers	0.10	0.03
3.	Producer's sale price	350.20	90.6
4.	Marketing cost incurred by retailers	0.50	0.12
5.	Retailers net margin	20.20	4.72
6.	Total marketing cost	0.90	0.12
7.	Total marketing margin	20.40	4.47
8.	Consumer's price	392.20	99.94

Table 3.3: Price Spread for Marketing in Channel- III

(Producer – wholesaler - retailer - consumer) Rs. /kg

S.NO.	Particulars	Rs.	Percentage%
1.	Net price received by the producers	250.75	55.83
2.	Marketing cost incurred by producers	0.35	0.15
3.	Producer's sale price	260.00	55.89
4.	Marketing cost incurred by Wholesaler	10.0	2.33
5.	Wholesaler net margin	10.25	2.42

Market margin and price spread for cited three channels displayed in table

CHANNEL-I

Producer – consumer

It was observed that producer's share in consumer's rupee was maximum in this channels. There was no middleman in these channels. Thus this channel was most appropriate from the view point of the producer and consumer.

CHANNEL – II

Producer – retailer - consumer

In this channel producer's share in consumer rupee was 95.8% which was lower than channel I. while marketing cost incurred by middleman was 0.18% and middleman margin 5.92%.

CHANNEL – III

Producer – retailer – wholesaler – consumer

It was found that this channel was not long. Only one middleman was present. In this channel Producer's in consumer rupee was 55.18%. Marketing cost incurred by middleman was lowest (2.33%) and middleman margin was 4.60%.

6.	Wholesalers sale price	120.25	27.43
7.	Marketing cost incurred by retailers	0.15	0.03
8.	Retailer's net margin	10.10	2.24
9.	Total marketing cost	10.20	2.31
10.	Total marketing margin	20.15	4.41
11.	Consumer's price	441.1	97.06

Inter channels comparison as a whole. Inter channel comparison of price spread, the marketing cost and margin is displayed in table 3.3. Inter channels comparison revealed that the producer's share in consumer rupee was maximum in channel I against other channels. Marketing incurred by producer went up with the increase in the intermediaries. By comparing to channel II. Channel III marketing cost incurred by the middleman channel III was high compared to the other channel.

Table: 3.4. Per cent price spread of milk under different marketing channels

S. NO.	Particulars	I	II	III
1.	Net price received by the producers	99.79	90.3	55.83
2.	Producer's sale price	-	90.6	55.89
3.	Marketing cost incurred by producers	0.10	0.03	0.15
4.	Wholesalers purchase price	-	-	60.27
5.	Wholesalers sale price	-	-	27.43
6.	Marketing cost incurred by Wholesaler	-	-	2.33
7.	Wholesaler net margin	-	-	2.42
8.	Retailer's purchase price	-	94.7	60.27
9.	Marketing cost incurred by retailers	-	0.12	0.03
10.	Retailer's net margin	-	4.72	2.24
11.	Total marketing cost	-	0.12	2.31
12.	Consumer's purchase price in per cent	100	100	100

Inter channel comparison as a whole. Inter channel comparison of price spread marketing cost and margin is displayed in table no. 4.4.4. Inter channels comparison revealed that the producer's share in consumer rupee was maximum in channel I against other channels. Marketing incurred by producer went up with the increase in the intermediaries. By comparing to the channel II. Channel III marketing cost incurred by the middleman channel III was high compared to the other channel.

Marketing efficiency:

The marketing efficiency of each channel is analysed and presented in table

Marketing efficiency index (MEI) represents the effectiveness of a marketing system in which it operates.

Comparison of CHANNEL I, II, III

Marketing efficiency, marketing cost, Price spread, Market margin of Namaste India in different channels.

Table 3.5: Total marketing costs includes marketing cost and profit margin of intermediaries

S.NO.	Particulars	Rs./kg		
		Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
1.	Consumer's price	350.60	392.20	441.1
2.	Total marketing cost (price spread)	0.30	38.5	189.48
3.	Marketing efficiency	1.31	1.25	1.76
4.	% Producer share in consumer rupee	99.79	90.30	55.83
5.	Total margin	78.40	20.80	21.25

It is observed from this efficiency index that channel I was the most efficient one. This is because channel I involves only few intermediaries and hence, it is the most efficient among the four identified channels.

Table 3.6: Price Spread for Marketing in Channel- I
(Producer – consumer) Rs. /kg

S.NO.	Particulars	Rs.	Percentage%
1.	Net price received by the producers	350.0	99.79
2.	Marketing cost incurred by producers	0.30	0.10
3.	Total marketing cost	0.30	0.10
4.	Consumer's price	350.60	99.99

Table 3.7: Price Spread for Marketing in Channel- II
(Producer – retailer - consumer)Rs. /kg

S.NO.	Particulars	Rs.	Percentage%
1.	Net price received by the producers	350.1	90.3
2.	Marketing cost incurred by producers	0.10	0.03
3.	Producer's sale price	350.20	90.6
4.	Marketing cost incurred by retailers	0.50	0.12
5.	Retailers net margin	20.20	4.72
6.	Total marketing cost	0.90	0.12
7.	Total marketing margin	20.40	4.47
8.	Consumer's price	392.20	99.94

Table 3.8: Price Spread for Marketing in Channel- III
(Producer – wholesaler - retailer - consumer) Rs. /kg

S.NO.	Particulars	Rs.	Percentage%
1.	Net price received by the producers	250.75	55.83
2.	Marketing cost incurred by producers	0.35	0.15
3.	Producer's sale price	260.00	55.89
4.	Marketing cost incurred by Wholesaler	10.0	2.33
5.	Wholesaler net margin	10.25	2.42
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11.	Consumer's price	441.1	97.06

Inter channels comparison as a whole. Inter channel comparison of price spread, the marketing cost and margin is displayed in table 4.4.3 Inter channels comparison revealed that the producer's share in consumer rupee was maximum in channel I against other channels.

Marketing incurred by producer went up with the increase in the intermediaries. By comparing to channel II. Channel III marketing cost incurred by the middleman channel III was high compared to the other channel.

Table: 3.9 Per cent price spread of milk under different marketing channels

S. NO.	Particulars	I	II	III
1.	Net price received by the producers	99.79	90.3	55.83
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12.	Consumer's purchase price in per cent	100	100	100

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Comparison of CHANNEL I, II, III

Marketing efficiency, marketing cost, Price spread, Market margin of Namaste India in different channels.

Table 3.10 Total marketing costs includes marketing cost and profit margin of intermediaries

S.NO.	Particulars	Rs./kg		
		Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
1.	Consumer's price	350.60	392.20	441.1
2.	Total marketing cost (price spread)	0.30	38.5	189.48
3.	Marketing efficiency	1.31	1.25	1.76
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It is observed from this efficiency index that channel I was the most efficient one. This is because channel I involves only few intermediaries and hence, it is the most efficient among the four identified channels.

Summary and Conclusion:

Summary:

India is the leading producer and consumer of milk across the globe. The Indian dairy sector is divided into the organized and mostly unorganized (75%). There is a need for investment, especially for the small and marginal dairy farmers to catalyze Indian dairy production and exports.

India has the largest bovine population of over 300 million, producing 198.4 million tones of milk in 2019-20. Despite COVID-19 induced restrictions, the organized sector is projected for a 5-6% growth i.e. Rs 1.5 lakh crore sectoral revenue generation in 2021-22, as per CRISIL.

In the previous year 2020-21, the VAPs (value-added products) and sales dropped due to pandemic-induced restrictions. However, continuity of food delivery and increase in household consumption has led to a surge in demand for VAPs and liquid milk in 2021-22. This shall also lead to increased procurement prices.

It was found that this channel was not long. Only one middleman was present. In this channel Producer's in consumer rupee was 58.13%. Marketing cost incurred by middleman was lowest (2.41%) and middleman margin was 4.71%.

Conclusions:

From the survey conducted it is observed that dairy Industry has good distribution channel in the market. From the study it is observed that factors which make its distribution channel effective are on time delivery, quality products, no damage to products, fast and effective supply chain.

Dairy Industry is huge base of membership, good net worth and support and support from government makes it a strong unit.

However, increasing complexities of the market and absence of pace can make a welfare unit. Efficient and dynamic management with strong leadership innovative strategies and proactive decision making can help dairy Industry to improve its performance in the market.

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